

Local Classification Around the Special Case of a Planar Mechanism

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1. The equation of the connections of the flat mechanisms is expressed in algebraic form as follows: [4]:

$$F_i(U, V) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} F_i(x_1, \dots, x_m, x_{m+1}, \dots, x_{m+n}) = 0, i = \overline{1, m}, n \leq m \quad (1)$$

Here, $U = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_m)$ va $V = (x_{m+1}, \dots, x_{m+n})$ are the state and control coordinates, respectively, and F_i -esa are polynomials. The number of equations is m , the number of state coordinates corresponds to U , and n is called the degree of freedom of the mechanism. In general, the degree of freedom of the mechanism is found by the equation $n=k-m$ [1], where k is the number of unknowns in the system of equations. Each value of the control coordinates V corresponds to a finite number of values of U satisfying the system (1). $U(V)$ is said to be a multivalued vector function, i.e, $x_i = x_i(x_{m+1}, \dots, x_{m+n})$ [2-3]:

Let us assume that the point $x_k^0 = (x_1, \dots, x_m, x_{m+1}, \dots, x_{m+n})$ satisfies the system of equations (1). Let us observe the state of the state function near this point. To do this, we construct the $m \times k$ -dimensional Jacobian matrix of the system (1):

$$J \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \left(\frac{\partial F_i}{\partial x_k} \right), i = \overline{1, m}, k = \overline{1, m+n}. \quad (2)$$

$1 \leq i_1 < i_2 < \dots < i_m \leq m+n$ Let there be some m -ordered set of integers, denoted by $I=(i_1, \dots, i_m)$. By M_I we denote the m -order minors of matrix (2), i.e., obtained by selecting the columns with indices $i_1, \dots, i_m$ in it.

Consider the following case [1]:

If $\forall I, M_I(x_k^0) \neq 0$, then we call the point x_k^0 a simple point of the system (1);

If $\exists I', I'', M_{I'}(x_k^0) = 0, M_{I''}(x_k^0) \neq 0$, then we call the point x_k^0 a special point of the first kind of the system of equations (1).

If $\exists I', I'', M_{I'}(x_k^0) = 0, M_{I''}(x_k^0) \neq 0$, then we call the point x_k^0 a special point of the second kind of the system of equations (1).

The solution of system (1) around a simple point can be described in the form of absolutely converging series, based on the Cauchy theorem on indeterminate functions:

$$x_i - x_i^0 = \varphi_i(x_{m+j} - x_{m+j}^0), i = \overline{1, m}, j = \overline{1, n}, \quad (3)$$

In this case, φ_i -order series. Accordingly, the state of the mechanism at this point is simple. The special states of the mechanism around the first and second special points coincide. Around the special point, the state function $U(V)$ ceases to be a single-valued analytic function of the control coordinates V . Around the second special case (dead state), the solution

of system (1) cannot be expressed in the form (3), since in this case the conditions of the theorem on non-obvious functions are not fulfilled. Therefore, using the Newton polynomial method, we can obtain parametric solutions of the form [2-3]:

$$x_i = x_i^0 + \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} b_{ij} \tau^{p_{ij}}, i = 1, m \quad (4)$$

2. Rectangular hydrocylinder mechanism. Let us look for an asymptotic solution of this mechanism around a special case. In this case, the points A, O, B, C have the following coordinates: $O(0,0), A(x_1, y_1), B(x_2, y_2), C(x_3, y_3)$ va $AB = a, BC = a$ - unchanging positive quantity, L_1, L_2 - positive variable.

Fig-1.

The coupling equations of the state functions of the mechanism under consideration have the following form:

$$\begin{cases} g_1 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} x_1^2 + y_1^2 = L_1^2 \\ g_2 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (x_1 - x_2)^2 + (y_1 - y_2)^2 = a^2 \\ g_3 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (x_2 - x_3)^2 + (y_2 - y_3)^2 = a^2 \\ g_4 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} x_3^2 + y_3^2 = L_2^2 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

System (1) has 4 equations and 8 unknowns, which means that it has $n=4$ degrees of freedom, that is, it consists of a mechanism with 4 degrees of freedom. The (4x8) Jacobian matrix of system (1) looks like this::

$$J = 2 \begin{pmatrix} x_1 & y_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -L_1 & 0 \\ x_1 - x_2 & y_1 - y_2 & x_2 - x_1 & y_2 - y_1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & x_2 - x_3 & y_2 - y_3 & x_3 - x_2 & y_3 - y_2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & x_3 & y_3 & 0 & -L_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

The number of nonzero minors of the Jacobi matrix of order 4 is 55, and they are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
M_1 &= 16x_3(y_1(x_2^2 - x_2^2x_3) + y_2(x_1x_3 - x_1x_2)); \\
M_2 &= 16y_3((x_2^2 - x_2x_3) - x_1x_2y_2); M_3 = 16L_2((x_2y_1 - x_1y_2)(x_2 - x_3)); \\
M_4 &= 16y_3(y_3(x_1^2 - x_1x_2) + y_1(x_1x_2 - x_1x_3) + y_2(x_1x_3 - x_1^2)); \\
M_5 &= 16y_1(x_1x_2x_3 - x_1^2x_3^2) + y_2(x_1x_3^2 - x_1^2x_3) + y_3(x_1^2x_3 - x_1x_2x_3); \\
M_6 &= 16L_2y_1(x_1^2 + x_1x_2 - x_1x_3) + L_2y_3(x_1x_2 + x_3^2) - x_1x_2y_2L_2; \\
M_7 &= 16y_3(x_1x_3y_3 + x_1x_2y_1 - x_1x_2y_1) - x_1x_3y_1y_2; \\
M_8 &= 16x_3L_1(y_2(x_1 - x_2) - y_3(x_2 + x_1)); \\
M_9 &= 16x_1L_2(y_1(x_2 - x_3) - y_3(x_3 + x_2)); \\
M_{10} &= 16L_1(x_3y_2(x_1 - x_2) + y_3(x_2^2 - x_1x_2)); \\
M_{11} &= 16L_1L_2(x_2y_2 + y_3(x_1 - x_2)); \\
M_{12} &= 16x_3(L_2(x_1y_2 - x_2y_1) + x_2y_1y_2 - x_2^2y_2^2); \\
M_{13} &= 16L_1(L_1(x_1y_2 - x_2y_1) + (x_2y_1y_2 - x_1y_2^2)); \\
M_{14} &= 16L_2(x_1(y_2^2 - x_2y_2) + y_3(x_2y_1 - x_1y_2)); \\
M_{15} &= 16x_2(x_3(x_1y_2 - x_2y_1) + x_3y_1y_2) - x_1x_3y_2^2; \\
M_{16} &= 16L_2(y_1(x_2^2 - x_2x_3) + y_2(x_1x_3 - x_1x_2)); \\
M_{17} &= 16(x_1x_2 - x_1^2)(x_1x_3 - x_2L_2); M_{18} = 16x_3L_1(x_1x_2 - x_2^2 + x_3(x_2 - x_1)); \\
M_{19} &= 16L_2x_1(x_1^2 - x_2^2 + x_1x_2 - x_2x_3); \\
M_{20} &= 16L_1y_3(x_2 - x_1)(y_3 - y_2); \\
M_{21} &= 16L_2x_1(y_2 - y_1)(y_2 - y_3); \\
M_{22} &= 16L_2x_1y_1(y_3 - y_2); \\
M_{23} &= 16x_3y_1(y_3(x_1 - x_2) + x_3(y_2 - y_1) + x_2y_1^2); \\
M_{24} &= 16y_1y_3(y_3(x_1 - x_2) + y_1(x_2 - x_3) + y_2(x_3 - x_1)); \\
M_{25} &= 16L_2y_1(y_3(x_2 - x_1) + y_2(x_1 - x_3) + y_1(x_3 - x_2)); \\
M_{26} &= 16y_1(y_2 - y_1)(x_3y_2 - x_2y_3); M_{27} = 16x_3L_2(y_1 - y_2)(y_3 - y_2) \\
M_{28} &= 16y_1L_2(x_2 - x_3)(y_2 - y_1); \\
M_{29} &= 16y_3L_1(y_3(y_2 - y_1) + 3y_1y_2 - 2y_2^2 - y_1^2); \\
M_{30} &= 16L_2(y_1^2(y_3 - y_2) + y_1(y_1^2 - y_2y_3)); M_{31} = 16L_1L_2(y_2 - y_1)(y_2 - y_3); \\
M_{32} &= 16(x_2 - x_1)(x_3y_1y_2 - x_2y_1y_3); \\
M_{33} &= 16x_3L_1(y_2(x_3 - x_2) + y_1(x_2 + x_3)); \\
M_{34} &= 16(x_1 - x_2)(x_3 - x_2)y_1L_2; M_{35} = 16L_1L_2(x_2 - x_3)(y_1 - y_2); \\
M_{36} &= 16y_2y_3L_1(y_1 - y_2)(1 + y_3); M_{37} = 16y_1L_2(y_3 - y_2)(y_1 - y_2); \\
M_{38} &= 16L_1L_2(x_2 - x_3)(y_2 - y_1); \\
M_{39} &= 16y_3L_1(y_3(x_1 - x_2) + y_1(x_2 - x_3) - x_1y_2); \\
M_{40} &= 16L_1(x_1 - x_2)(x_2y_3 - x_3y_2); M_{41} = 16(x_2 - x_1)(y_3 - y_2)L_1L_2;
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_{42} &= 16(x_2 - x_1)(x_3 - x_2)L_1L_2; & M_{43} &= 16y_3L_1(y_1(x_3 - y_1) + x_2(y_1 - y_2)); \\
 M_{44} &= 16(y_2 - y_1)(x_3 - x_2)L_1L_2; & M_{45} &= 16(y_2 - y_1)(y_3 - y_1)L_1L_2; \\
 M_{46} &= 16L_1L_2(x_1 - x_2)(x_3 - x_2); & M_{47} &= L_1L_2(y_3 - y_2)(x_2 - x_1); \\
 M_{48} &= 16L_1L_2(x_1 - x_1)(x_3 - x_2); & M_{49} &= 16(x_2 - x_1)(x_3 - x_1)y_3L_1; \\
 M_{50} &= 16x_1L_2(y_2 - y_3)(x_2 - x_1); & M_{51} &= 16(x_3 - x_2)(x_1 - x_2)L_1L_2; \\
 M_{52} &= 16y_3L_1(x_1 - x_2)(y_2 - y_1); & M_{53} &= 16y_1L_2(x_1 - x_2)(y_3 - y_2); \\
 M_{54} &= 16L_1L_2(y_2 - y_1)(y_3 - y_2); \\
 M_{55} &= 16y_3L_1(y_3(x_1 - x_2) + y_1(x_2 - x_3) + y_2(x_3 - x_1)); \\
 M_{56} &= M_{57} = M_{58} = M_{59} = M_{60} = M_{61} = M_{62} = M_{63} = M_{64} = M_{65} = 0 \\
 M_{66} &= M_{67} = M_{68} = M_{69} = M_{70} = 0.
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem. The rectangular hydrocylindrical mechanism does not achieve the second kind of speciality.

Proof. According to the condition, for the mechanism to achieve the second kind of speciality, the condition $M_i = 0$ ($i = \overline{1,70}$) must be satisfied for $\forall i$ (Figure 5). However, this does not happen, because, according to the definition, $L_1, L_2 > 0$. The theorem is proved.

Fig-2

$$x_1 = x_2 = 0;$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_1 &= M_3 = M_4 = M_5 = M_7 = M_8 = M_{10} = M_{11} = M_{12} = M_{13} = M_{14} = 0, \\
 M_{15} &= M_{16} = M_{17} = M_{18} = M_{19} = M_{20} = M_{21} = M_{22} = M_{32} = M_{34} = 0, \\
 M_{40} &= M_{41} = M_{46} = M_{47} = M_{49} = M_{50} = M_{51} = M_{53} = 0.
 \end{aligned}$$

Fig-3

$$x_3 = x_2 = 0$$

$$M_1 = M_2 = M_3 = M_5 = M_8 = M_9 = M_{10} = M_{12} = M_{15} = M_{16} = M_{17} = M_{18} = 0$$

$$M_{23} = M_{26} = M_{28} = M_{32} = M_{33} = M_{35} = M_{38} = M_{42} = M_{44} = M_{46} = 0$$

$$M_{48} = M_{51} = 0$$

Fig-4

$$x_1 = x_2 = x_3 = 0, L_1 = L_2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_1 = M_2 = M_3 = M_4 = M_5 = M_6 = M_7 = M_8 = M_9 = M_{10} = M_{11} = M_{12} &= 0 \\
 M_{13} = M_{14} = M_{15} = M_{16} = M_{17} = M_{18} = M_{19} = M_{20} = M_{21} = M_{22} = M_{23} &= 0 \\
 M_{24} = M_{25} = M_{26} = M_{27} = M_{28} = M_{32} = M_{34} = M_{35} = M_{38} = M_{39} = M_{40} = M_{41} &= 0 \\
 M_{41} = M_{42} = M_{44} = M_{45} = M_{46} = M_{47} = M_{48} = M_{49} = M_{50} = M_{51} = M_{52} &= 0 \\
 M_{53} = M_{55} &= 0
 \end{aligned}$$

Fig-5

$$y_1 = y_2 = y_3 = 0, \begin{cases} x_1 = -a \\ x_2 = 0 \\ x_3 = a \end{cases}, \begin{cases} L_1 = -a \\ L_2 = a \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 M_1 = M_2 = M_3 = M_4 = M_5 = M_6 = M_7 = M_8 = M_9 = M_{10} = M_{11} = M_{12} &= 0 \\
 M_{13} = M_{14} = M_{15} = M_{16} = M_{17} = M_{20} = M_{21} = M_{22} = M_{23} = M_{24} = M_{25} &= 0 \\
 M_{26} = M_{27} = M_{28} = M_{29} = M_{30} = M_{31} = M_{32} = M_{33} = M_{34} = M_{35} = M_{36} &= 0 \\
 M_{39} = M_{38} = M_{40} = M_{41} = M_{43} = M_{44} = M_{45} = M_{47} = M_{49} = M_{50} = M_{52} &= 0 \\
 M_{53} = M_{54} = M_{55} &= 0
 \end{aligned}$$

Now, using the Newton polynomial method, we search for parametric solutions of system (1) around the special case P⁵. Here, P⁵ (-a, 0, a, 0, 0, 0 - a, a)

(Figure 5.) Let us assume the following coordinate transformations in system (5).

$$\begin{cases} x_1 = -a + t_1, \\ x_2 = t_2, \\ x_3 = a + t_3, \\ y_1 = t_4, \\ y_2 = t_5, \\ y_3 = t_6, \\ L_1 = -a + t_7, \\ L_2 = a + t_8. \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Here t_i ($i = \overline{1,8}$) are local deviations from the special case P^5 . Substituting these values into system (1), we obtain the following system::

$$\begin{aligned} g_1 &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (-a + t_1)^2 + t_4^2 = (-a + t_7)^2; \\ g_2 &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (-a + t_1 - t_2)^2 + (t_4 - t_5)^2 = a^2; \\ g_3 &\stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (t_2 - (a + t_3))^2 + (t_5 - t_6)^2 = a^2; \\ g_4 &= (a + t_3)^2 + t_6^2 = (a + t_8)^2; \end{aligned}$$

After performing the appropriate calculations and taking into account the conditions of system (1), we arrive at the following system:

$$\begin{aligned} t_1^2 - 2at_1 + t_4^2 + 2at_7 - t_7^2 &= 0 \\ t_1^2 - 2at_1 - 2t_1t_2 + 2at_2 + t_2^2 + t_4^2 - 2t_4t_5 + t_5^2 &= 0 \\ t_3^2 + 2at_3 - 2at_2 - 2t_2t_3 + t_2^2 + t_4^2 - 2t_4t_5 + t_5^2 &= 0 \\ t_3^2 + 2at_3 + t_6^2 - 2at_8 - t_8^2 &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Using Newton's polynomial method, we obtain the following abbreviated system for system (7).

$$\begin{aligned} t_4^2 + 2at_7 - 2at_1 &= 0 \\ 2at_2 - 2at_1 - 2t_1t_2 - 2t_4t_5 &= 0 \\ 2at_3 - 2at_2 - 2t_2t_3 - 2t_5t_6 &= 0 \\ 2at_3 - 2at_8 + t_6^2 &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

Solve this system:

$$\begin{aligned} t_1 &= t_7 + \frac{t_4^2}{2a} = t_7 + \frac{1}{2a} \left(\frac{a(t_8(2a^2 + 2at_7) - t_6^2(a + t_7) + 2a^2t_7 - 2at_5t_6)}{t_8(2a^2 + 2at_5) + 2t_5(a^2 - t_6^2 - at_6) - at_6^2} \right)^2 \\ t_2 &= \frac{a(2at_8 - t_6^2 - 2t_5t_6)}{2a^2 + 2at_8 - t_6^2}; \quad t_3 = \frac{2at_8 - t_6^2}{2a}; \quad t_4 = \frac{a(t_8(2a^2 + 2at_7) - t_6^2(a + t_7) + 2a^2t_7 - 2at_5t_6)}{t_8(2a^2 + 2at_5) + 2t_5(a^2 - t_6^2 - at_6) - at_6^2} \end{aligned}$$

Substituting the values of t_i ($i = \overline{1,8}$) found into system (6), we obtain the asymptotic solution for system (5)

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} x_1 = -a + t_7 + \frac{1}{2a} \left(\frac{a(t_8(2a^2 + 2at_7) - t_6^2(a + t_7) + 2a^2t_7 - 2at_5t_6)}{t_8(2a^2 + 2at_5) + 2t_5(a^2 - t_6^2 - at_6) - at_6^2} \right)^2 + \dots; \\ x_2 = \frac{a(2at_8 - t_6^2 - 2t_5t_6)}{2a^2 + 2at_8 - t_6^2} + \dots; \\ x_3 = a + \frac{2at_8 - t_6^2}{2a} + \dots; \\ y_1 = \frac{a(t_8(2a^2 + 2at_7) - t_6^2(a + t_7) + 2a^2t_7 - 2at_5t_6)}{t_8(2a^2 + 2at_5) + 2t_5(a^2 - t_6^2 - at_6) - at_6^2} + \dots; \\ y_2 = t_5 + \dots; \\ y_3 = t_6 + \dots; \\ L_1 = -a + t_7 + \dots; \\ L_2 = a + t_8 + \dots \end{array} \right. \quad (8)$$

It can be seen from the obtained solutions (diagram 5), that the mechanism can move in different directions from such a special state, and by knowing them, it is possible to lose the special states of the mechanism in the necessary cases, that is, it is possible to ensure that the mechanism does not fall into special states by changing the parameters of the mechanism. it will be possible to provide.

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